

Education & Skills

March 2026

The Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development, building on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The project POLICY ANSWERS monitors the implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda, and the broader context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this Monitoring Card, you find the results of the third round of data collection in 2025 and at the beginning of 2026, in comparison to the data collected in the previous third monitoring round.

In terms of Education & Skills, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator “Academic Freedom Index” and various achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Source
Academic Freedom Index <https://academic-freedom-index.net/> (accessed 10 November 2025).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicators

Western Balkans Steering Platform meetings on Education and Training	Regional policy dialogue on education and training under the Berlin Process	Participation in ERA Forum group meetings & workshops
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Western Balkans Economy Indicators

Indicator and overall assessment of the region	Integration and stronger participation in EU programmes and initiatives				Fostered capacity building for R&I, education and Vocational Education and Training (VET)		
	Supporting the Implementation of the EU acquis	Stronger participation in VET processes	Promotion of WB participation under the MSCA	WB participation in Erasmus University Alliances	Encouraging education-driven and skills-based innovation	Capacity building in POLICY ANSWERS	
Albania	No Twinning project Not aligned with the Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG)	No meetings organised No commitments reported	Increased number of promotion and info meetings Increased number of MSCA projects including staff exchange (SE) projects	Increased participation in 4 University Alliances	Increased number of awareness/capacity building events and participants Participation in Digital Education Hackathons (DigiEduHack), national DigiEduHack ambassador assigned	Increased number of capacity building activities and beneficiaries	
Bosnia and Herzegovina	No Twinning project Not aligned with the ESG	Increased number of meetings and commitments reported	Increased number of promotion and info meetings Increased number of MSCA projects, no new SE project	Increased participation in 5 University Alliances	Increased number of awareness/capacity building events No participation in the DigiEduHack, no national ambassador assigned	Increased number of capacity building activities and beneficiaries	
Kosovo	No Twinning project Not aligned with the ESG	Information on meetings not provided Increased number of commitments reported	Increased number of promotion and info meetings No new MSCA projects, including SE projects	New participation in 1 University Alliance	Increased number of awareness/capacity building events and participants No participation in the DigiEduHack, no national ambassador assigned	Increased number of capacity building activities and beneficiaries	
Montenegro	Twinning project started Partially aligned with the ESG	Increased number of meetings and commitments reported	No information on promotion and info meetings provided Increased number of MSCA projects, including SE projects	Continuous participation in 1 University Alliance	No new events reported No participation in the DigiEduHack, national DigiEduHack ambassador assigned	Increased number of capacity building activities and beneficiaries	
North Macedonia	No Twinning projects Not aligned with the ESG	Increased number of meetings and commitments reported	Increased number of promotion and info meetings No new MSCA projects, including SE projects	Increased participation in 4 University Alliances	Increased number of awareness/capacity building events and participants No participation in the DigiEduHack, national DigiEduHack ambassador assigned	Increased number of capacity building activities and beneficiaries	
Serbia	No Twinning projects Not aligned with the ESG	Increased number of meetings and commitments reported	Increased number of promotion and info meetings Increased number of MSCA actions, including SE projects	Participation in 3 University Alliances	Increased number of awareness/capacity building events and participants Participation in DigiEduHack, national DigiEduHack ambassador assigned	Increased number of capacity building activities and beneficiaries	

Legend: On track or maintaining achievement | Moderately improving Challenges remain | Stagnating Significant challenges | Decreasing Major challenges | Information not available

Highlights

POLICY ANSWERS capacity building programmes carried out successfully - highlights include: technical assistance for Ministries, advancing thematic curricula, private-sector collaboration, Green and Digital Agenda implementation, creating synergies through Quadruple Helix Coordination Forum

Strengthening Research and Innovation in the Western Balkans: The POLICY ANSWERS project

POLICY ANSWERS is a strategic initiative funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe project "R&I POLICY making, implementation ANd Support in the WEStErN BalkanS". The project focuses on enhancing research and innovation (R&I) policymaking and governance systems in the Western Balkans, while also addressing aspects of education, culture, youth, and sports. By providing essential support to the region's development, POLICY ANSWERS plays a crucial role in strengthening the Western Balkans' potential for successful participation in regional and multilateral research and innovation activities.

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POLICY ANSWERS, "R&I POLICY making, implementation ANd Support in the WEStErN BalkanS", is a Horizon Europe project funded by the European Commission, Grant Agreement N° 101058873.